

Sixty percent of the women farmers were directly involved in rice cultivation, distributed in each category as follows: doing the work herself (27.1%), assisting (8.8%), and supervising (24.1%). They played a distinct and well-accepted role in such activities as pulling out seedlings (80.8%), transporting (62.5%), transplanting seedlings (94.2%), harvesting (100%), bundling (90%), heaping the bundles (98.3%), thrashing (93.3%), win-

nowing (87.5%), bagging (91.6%), and storing of grains (93.3%). Women farmers with small land did the activities themselves to reduce cultivation costs and thereby increase net income. On the other hand, women farmers with big farms often paid others to assist in and supervise the process of cultivation.

The results imply that technology development and transfer should consider specific characteristics and needs of women in

the conduct of rice production activities. This will enhance efficiency in different farming operations and boost farm productivity and net profit.

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Farmers' participatory evaluation of BRR1 hybrid dhan 1 in Bangladesh

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Farmers' participatory evaluation of rice varieties refers to the active involvement of farmers in the process of selecting varieties. It enables one to understand the criteria and approaches used by farmers in deciding what variety to grow (Hawlader 2001). BRR1 hybrid dhan 1, the first hybrid rice variety developed by the BRR1 and released in 2001, was evaluated using a participatory approach at on-station (BRR1 Regional Station, Bhanga, Faridpur) and on-farm (13 villages of Faridpur District) trials in 2002 boro (dry season). In many countries, this approach is commonly used to identify farmers' preferred varieties. In Nepal, varieties selected through participatory evaluation yielded 15–18% more than existing varieties (Sthapit et al 1996). In view of the very little work done on participatory

evaluation of hybrid rice in Bangladesh, this study used a participatory approach to learn farmers' preferences and opinions about hybrid rice.

On-station trials evaluated BRR1 hybrid dhan 1, three imported hybrids (Sonar Bangla, Alook, and Jagoron), two popular inbred varieties (BINA dhan 5 and BINA dhan 6), and one popular inbred check variety (BRR1 dhan 29). All the test varieties were grown side by side with the check variety. Plot size was 20 m × 10 m. The on-farm experiment used BRR1 dhan 29, a popular boro rice variety, as a check for comparison with BRR1 hybrid dhan 1. Plot size was 20 m × 20 m. Forty-day-old seedlings of each variety were transplanted at a spacing of 20 cm × 15 cm with 1–2 seedlings per hill. Standard agronomic practices were followed.

Field evaluation of crop cuts of test and check varieties was done at crop maturity. Farmers, officials of the Directorate of Agricultural Extension and Seed Certification Agency, BRR1 scientists, newspaper reporters, and local leaders were present at the occasion. Through brainstorming sessions, group discussions, and matrix rankings, 200 participating farmers identified the characters of a rice hybrid that they preferred.

Results of on-station trials revealed that BRR1 hybrid dhan 1 took 163 d to mature and its grain yield was 8.2 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). BRR1 hybrid dhan 1 exhibited the highest productivity (50.3 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹), followed by BRR1 dhan 29 (44.6 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹), Sonar Bangla (44.5 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹), and Alook (38.4 kg ha⁻¹ d⁻¹). BRR1 hybrid dhan 1 showed a 12.8% increased productivity over BRR1 dhan 29.

Table 1. Performance of some hybrid and inbred rice varieties, BIRRI Regional Station, Bhanga, Faridpur, during 2002 boro.

Hybrid/inbred variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Grain sterility (%)	Days to maturity	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Productivity (kg ha ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	Increased productivity over check (%)
BIRRI hybrid dhan 1	102.7	285	136.4	20.1	163	8.2	50.3	12.8
Sonar Bangla	85.3	260	130.0	7.4	155	6.9	44.5	-0.2
Alook	84.8	272	123.4	22.3	151	5.8	38.4	-13.9
Jagoron	83.0	220	127.0	17.3	155	5.9	38.1	-14.8
BINA dhan 5	99.5	192	99.8	14.4	156	5.4	34.6	-22.4
BINA dhan 6	107.0	208	126.0	17.1	172	6.3	36.6	-17.9
BIRRI dhan 29 (check)	99.6	255	132.0	15.5	166	7.4	44.6	-
Mean	94.6	227.4	124.9	16.3	159.7	6.6	41.0	-
CV (%)	10.5	15.3	9.5	29.2	4.7	15.1	14.4	-

Table 2. Comparative productivity of BIRRI hybrid dhan 1 and BIRRI dhan 29 grown in 13 villages of Faridpur District, 2002 boro.

Location (village)	BIRRI dhan 29			BIRRI hybrid dhan 1			Increased productivity over BIRRI dhan 29 (%)
	Days to maturity	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Productivity (kg ha ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	Days to maturity	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Productivity (kg ha ⁻¹ d ⁻¹)	
Tuzarpur	165	8.5	51.5	157	9.0	57.7	12.0
Khapura	162	7.0	43.2	158	7.4	46.8	8.3
Brahmankanda	161	8.0	49.7	157	8.5	54.1	8.9
Mansurabad	164	8.6	52.4	159	9.5	59.7	13.9
Poranpur	162	6.8	42.0	156	7.0	44.9	6.9
Laxmipur	160	7.0	42.4	159	7.3	45.9	8.3
Deora	161	7.5	46.6	160	7.5	47.8	2.6
Nidhirampur	160	7.3	45.6	158	8.0	50.6	11.0
Gongadhardi	162	7.5	45.5	159	8.8	55.3	21.5
Sadardi	163	8.3	50.9	157	9.4	59.9	17.7
Mansurabad	164	8.0	48.8	159	9.0	56.6	16.0
Maligram	160	8.2	51.3	157	8.6	54.8	6.8
Hazrakanda	162	7.8	48.1	159	8.0	50.3	4.6
Mean	162	7.8	47.5	158.1	8.3	52.6	10.7
CV (%)	1.7	7.1	7.3	3.0	10.0	9.6	-

On-farm results showed that BIRRI hybrid dhan 1 took 158.1 d to mature; grain yield was 8.3 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2). The increased productivity of BIRRI hybrid dhan 1 over BIRRI dhan 29 ranged from 2.6% to 21.5% (the mean was

10.7%). Similarly, Hawlader et al (2002) reported 7 d earliness and a 14.2% increase in grain yield of BIRRI hybrid dhan 1 over BIRRI dhan 29 during on-farm trials in 2000-01 boro.

BIRRI hybrid dhan 1 was preferred because of its uniformity, high grain and stover yield, long panicles, high filled grains/panicle, and low grain sterility and shattering. The farmers did not consider grain yield as the sole criterion for varietal selection. Also considered important were the production of sufficient straw, less grain shattering in the field, cold tolerance at the seedling stage, good market value, easy threshing quality, and lower seed price (Hawlader 2001). The farmers also wanted the cost of hybrid seed to be reasonable; the hybrid variety to fit into their cropping patterns, to adapt to the local environment, and to meet household requirements; and the required management practices to be affordable. The adoption rate of BIRRI hybrid dhan 1 may be increased if farmers participate in its evaluation.

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